

Secondary School Students' Attitude towards the Health Implications of Early Marriage in the Izzi Local Government Area

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Abstract

The study examines the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the health implications of early marriage with a view of ascertaining the variables (gender, age and types of studentship) that influence the attitude towards the health implications. In line with the objectives of the study, six research questions and three hypotheses were formulated. Related literature on attitude towards health implication of early marriage were reviewed. Descriptive survey research design was utilized. The accessible population for the study consisted of all the senior secondary school students in Izzi Local Government Area. A total of 400 students were used for the study. The instrument for data collection was self-developed questionnaire. Validity of the instrument was ensured through constructive criticism of three lecturers in the Department of physical and health Education, Ikwo College of Education Ebonyi. A test re-test reliability ($r = 0.81$) of the instrument was ensured. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequencies, percentages, mean as well as inferential statistics of chi-square (X^2). Based on the findings, conclusions were drawn among which are that 77% appreciable percentage of the respondents revealed negative attitude towards the physical, social and emotional health implications of early marriage. Equally gender, age and type of studentship had significant influence on the attitude of secondary school students towards health implications of early marriage. Recommendations were made, pertinent among which is that health education campaign should be organized by the Ministry of Women Affairs and Ministry of Education towards changing the attitude of the general public concerning early marriage.

Keywords: attitude, health implications early marriage, secondary school students, Izzi local government area.

INTRODUCTION

Everywhere in the globe, getting married is seen as a joyous occasion and important turning point for adults. It is a method through which people choose their life companions. It is an institution that controls when men and women reproduce in accordance with established and recognized social standards. Marriage is the union of a man and a woman so they can coexist, reproduce, raise children, support one another, and establish a happy medium [1].

Marriage is the state of being joined as husband or wife to a person of the other sex in a legal, consenting, and contractual relationship that is recognized and governed by law and can only be dissolved by it [2]. It is a man and woman's legal relationship as husband and wife. It went on to clarify that marriage is a contract that is legally binding between two people and unites their lives, finances, and assets. The man and lady have made an agreement. The husband and wife make a number of commitments to one another throughout the marriage ceremony, including promises to love and cherish one another and to be together through good times and bad. Marriage has long been a feature of human experience, it was noted [3]. It strengthens links between families and groups and is an essential component of the economic and political system [4]. Since marriage is a legal-religious contract under which a man and a woman are legally wedded, it was stated that Gen. 3:24 was created to ensure that it would be advantageous for both parents, the families involved, and society at large [5].

It's been said that marriage transforms an imperfect person into a whole one. It organizes one's life, taking one out of the fast-paced atmosphere they are in and placing them in a structured environment where they have a course to follow and someone to lean on [6]. According to another perspective, marriage creates a relationship between the man and the woman. It serves as a means of bringing kids into the world. She continued by saying that it fosters marital harmony and makes families happier by allowing husbands and wives to support one another. Marriage has a proper period known as the idea time for both the man and the woman to come together as husband and wife, despite the fact that it was founded by God for the benefit of mankind [7].

Perse, marriage is an adult relationship; it is not for little children or newborns. It was emphasized that in addition to understanding, patience, and trust, maturity is one of the qualities needed in a marriage. Marriage is a commitment, and only responsible adults who can cope with life's challenges can succeed. There is no set age limit for getting married. It should only be used by mature individuals who have experienced life and can understand what it's all about as well as make their own decisions. The author made the observation that getting married at the age of 21 would sound ideal for someone who is advised by their doctor to have all of their children before they are 25 years old owing to a medical problem. He also said that for a lady who is successful at her high-powered work, getting married at the age of 32 sounds excellent. Onuzulike (2006) observed that the right age for marriage should be 20 years for females and 28 years for males. Wang, Healy, Black, and Sullivan (2003) noted that the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, 1990 established the minimum age for marriage to be 18 years. Early marriage is defined as any union that takes place before the customary or appropriate time. [8]

According to Article 1 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, an early marriage is any union of a child under the age of 18 years. Early marriage, according to the UNICEF Innocenti Research Center, is when a kid or adolescent marries before turning 18 years old. The center also stated that among those leading traditional lifestyles in underdeveloped nations, marriage occurs frequently soon after puberty [9]. It was claimed that marriage is regarded premature when the parties involved cannot physically, socially, economically, psychologically, or morally support a family unit. Additionally, she outlined how sociologically, a girl or guy marries before the age of eighteen or twenty-one, respectively [10]. The act of entering into a marital or status relationship too soon, whether on the part of a male or female person, is known as an early marriage. Being too young in terms of age and not being physically and psychologically prepared to carry out fatherhood activities and associated responsibilities may be the cause of marriage being premature [11]. Typically, young marriages are arranged by girls. Because of the pervasive gender imbalance in society, girls frequently lack the abilities and negotiation strength of boys. Early marriage is not something that just happens; there are things that can lead to it [12].

Strong social traditions, family pressure, an unfavorable home environment, higher educational expectations, ongoing conflict with siblings, societal culture, school dropouts, early maturity, peer group influence, promiscuity, parent styles, the proliferation of pornographic materials, large family sizes, and a down economy are some of the factors that contribute to early marriage [13]. The following are some factors that may make secondary school students more likely to get married young: the fear of contracting the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) drives men to look for younger partners in many countries; some parents believe that early marriage is one way to protect young girls; some families encourage their daughters to get married young to avoid the threat of kidnapping and poverty. The center also claimed that in Somalia, families would wed their daughters to militiamen in exchange for the men's security and that of the families' own. Early marriage has numerous negative health effects on women, men, families, and society at large [14].

The idea that getting married before being physically and mentally capable has many negative impacts on the partners, especially women. The health effects of early marriage would be examined in this article under the topics of physical health effects, social health complications, and emotional health effects [15].

The adolescent girl being pregnant could have consequences for her physical health. Nzeako (2006) noted that anaemia, premature labor, eclampsia, or fits during pregnancy, high blood pressure, obstructed labor, as well as a higher chance of STDs, are some of the physical health effects of early marriage that may occur from teenage pregnancies [16]. Young adolescent girls who get pregnant early have issues because their pelvic development isn't finished to allow for a safe delivery [17]. Early marriage and having children were found to be the main risk factors contributing to Bangladesh's high maternal death rate [18]. It was argued that having children too young, brides of early marriage are at a very high risk for fistulas, getting infected with STDs, and at an elevated risk of obesity and chronic anemia [19].

Early marriage has a significant impact on the child brides' social development. It was recognised that early marriage contributes to likely low educational attainment and lack of life skills, higher susceptibility to abuse, and extreme poverty. Early brides are more prone to experience abuse and violence. According to studies, women who marry young are more likely to believe that it is occasionally appropriate for a husband to physically abuse his wife and are also more likely to be the victims of domestic violence. The center went on to say that early marriage has been linked to increased

rates of divorce or separation as well as wife abandonment. The child brides also run the risk of losing their wives to their frequently abusive husbands [20]. It was added that young girls who married at a young age- also have a higher risk of becoming a victim of domestic violence, sexual abuse, and murder [21]. This is in addition to the withdrawal of females from formal schooling. The mother's typical life trajectory is disturbed by an early marriage. The young mother is thrust into a role for which she is only tangentially prepared and frequently feels unprepared to assume as a result of unplanned childbirth [21].

It is a great responsibility for a young girl to become a bride and mother, and since females are not sufficiently prepared for these duties, this heavy load has a major impact on their emotional wellbeing, how they see themselves, and how they interact with others. After being married and having a child, a young girl may start to feel a lot of stress, despair, depression, helplessness, low self-esteem, a sense of personal failure, suicidal thoughts, dread, frustration, perplexity, and resentment. Both rich and developing nations engage in early marriage [5].

Early marriage is reportedly a global occurrence, but it is most common in Africa and southern Asia [10]. According to the center, 42 percent of females in Africa get married before turning 18; in some African nations, this number is substantially higher. They went on to say that early marriage is thought to occur in Niger at a rate of 76 percent. Maternal mortality among teenage females in Bangladesh was found to be 580 per 100,000 live births, according to a study that was conducted. 70% of eclampsia patients are teenage moms, and many of them pass away from internal bleeding during childbirth or become infertile [11]. According to reports, there are extreme examples where 54 percent and 51 percent, respectively, of girls in Afghanistan and Bangladesh are married by the time they turn 18. In Nepal, an Asian country where the first marriage arrangement is 19 years, 7% of girls are married before the age of 10 and 40% by the age of 15. Early marriage is prevalent in Nigeria, according to a research done in the Afikpo South Local Government Area of Ebonyi State [14].

The rising rates of child and maternal morbidity and mortality in recent years may be attributable to teens' unfavorable attitudes concerning the detrimental effects of early marriage on their health. The way we feel and think about something is our attitude. An attitude is a set of ideas that are relatively persistently organized around a certain thing or circumstance, predisposing a person to respond in a particular way. It is a system of interconnected ideas that has a rather long history. These beliefs each have cognitive, emotive, and behavioral components and define, assess, and advise action in relation to a particular situation. [22] A person's attitude is their propensity to act, think, or feel favorably or unfavorably toward a certain thing, person, circumstance, or idea.

The minimum age for marriage, according to studies from numerous institutions, should be 18. The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, published in 1990, set an upper age limit of 18 years for marriage, while some argue that this should be 28 years for men and 20 years for women. All of these point to the conclusion that marriage is only appropriate for individuals who are both mentally and physically mature [23].

One of the essential elements of a successful marriage is maturity, along with comprehension, patience, and trust. Before performing the traditional rites in a marriage, the husband and wife must have decided to get married, and their families must have both granted their consent [5].

It is no longer news in our society that parents often force their adolescent daughters, especially girls, into early marriages for reasons related to finances, protection, or other matters best known to them. It is a well-known truth that these youths have children while they are still in their teenage years. when they are unable to make decisions for their families and themselves. Researchers are encouraged to learn secondary school students' attitudes on the health effects of early marriage in Izzi L.G.A. because of the rise in early marriage instances and their impact on the bride's overall development [24].

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive survey research design was utilized for the study.

Area of Study

The area of study is Izzi Local Government Area of Ebonyi State. It is one of the 13 local Government Areas in Ebonyi State. It was carved out of the old Abakaliki Local Government Area in October, 1987.

It is bounded in the North by Benue State, in the South by Abakaliki Local Government Area, in the East by Cross River State, and in the West by Ebonyi Local Government Area. It's administrative headquarters ie at Iboko. Izzi Local Government has eight (8) Autonomous communities namely: Agbaja, Ezzainyimagu, Ndiebor Ezzainyimagu, Ndiechi Ezzainyimagu, Igbeagu, Mgbalukwu, Ndieze and ndieze - Echi. Each of the autonomous Communities has a traditional ruler.

According to the 2006 census figure, Izzi Local Government Area has a total population of 234,072 made up of 110, 072 males and 124,000 females. Majority of the people of Izzi are farmers some are traders, others are civil servants and few are in politics.

The people of Izzi Local Government Area are generally hospitable and kind to strangers.

Population for the Study

The target population for the study consisted of all the senior secondary school students from SSI - SS III in all the secondary schools in Izzi L.G.A, totaling 4000 students from the randomly drawn secondary schools in the LG.A.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study consisted of 400 students from the senior classes in all the secondary schools in the Local Government Area. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select sample for the study.

In stage one, all the secondary schools in the Local Government Area were listed out using simple random sampling technique of balloting without replacement, five schools were drawn.

Stage two involved stratification of the subjects from the selected schools. Using simple random sampling technique, 10 percent of the subjects were selected from each of the selected secondary schools.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was self-developed questionnaire after a thorough review of the literature based on the objectives of the study. The questionnaire consists of four sections. Section A contained three questions on background information of the respondents. Section B contained eight questions that provide information based on the physical health implication of early marriage. Section C consists of eight questions on the social health implications of early marriage while Section D contained ten questions on emotional health implications of early marriage.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was approved by the project supervisor and validated by three other lecturers in the Department of physical and validated by three other lecturers in the Department of physical and Health Education, I.C.E.I Ebonyi. Their criticism, advice and suggestions were used in modifying the instrument that was used for data collection.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established through test re-rest technique. Ten copies of the questionnaire were distributed to ten students from Abakaliki Girls Secondary school, Abakaliki which was not part of the study population, similar the same characteristics with the study population. After two weeks, the same questions were given out to the same population. The test re-test results were analyzed using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Co-efficient. Result of the Study showed high positive correlation co-efficient of 0.81

Method of Data Collection

To gain access to the schools, a letter of introduction from the project supervisor seeking for permission was given to the principals' in-charge of each of the selected secondary schools. The purpose of the study was explained to them in order to gain their co-operation and that of the researchers with the help of the class teachers. Altogether 400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and collected thus given a return rate of 100%.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were tallied and analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage. The hypotheses were also analyzed using an inferential statistics of chi-square and tested at 05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table 1
Frequency distribution of respondents' gender

Gender	F	%
Male	140	35
Female	260	65
Total		

Table 1 reveals that out of 400 respondents, 140 (35%) were males while 260 (65%) were females.

Table 2
Frequency distribution of respondents' ages

Ages	F	%
13-14years	45	11.25
15-16 years	150	37.50
T17-18 years	125	31.25
19 years and above	80	20
Total	400	100

Table 2 above shows that out of 400 respondents' 45(11.25%) were within 13-14 years, 150(37.5%) were within the age bracket 15-16 years, 125(31.25%) were within 17-18 years, while 80(20%) were within the age bracket 19 years and above.

Table 3
Frequency distribution of respondent's type of studentship

Types of studentship	F	%
Boarding Students	110	27.5
Day Students	290	72.5
Total	400	100

Table 3 reveals that 110 (27.5%) of the respondents were boarding students while 290 (72.5%) were day students.

Research Question 1

What is the attitude of secondary school students Izzi L.G.A towards physical health implications of early marriage?

Physical health implications of early marriage	Attitudinal positive	Response Negative	Total
Early marriage can expose the teenage girls to maternal mortality	164(41%)	236(59%)	400
An adolescent mother who marries later can develop complication during pregnancy	143(35.75%)	257(64.25%)	400
A teenage girl who marries early has chances of suffering eclampsia (fit or convulsion) in pregnancy	120(30%)	280(70%)	400
Teenage pregnancy which may result from early marriage can lead to premature labour (ie is labour before nine months)	165(41.25%)	235(58.75%)	400
Early marriage can predispose the women to anaemia in pregnancy (shortage of blood).	260(65%)	140(35%)	400
Early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to higher risk of sexually transmitted infections such as HIV/AIDS.	245(62.25%)	155(38.75%)	400
Brides of early marriage are at an extremely high risk of contracting WF Vesioic Vaginal Fistula) and RVF (Recto vaginal fistula)	118(29.5%)	282(70.5%)	400
Young mothers are likely to suffer heavy bleeding in pregnancy.	145(36.25%)	255(63.75%)	400
Total	1360	1840	230
Grand percentage	(42.5%)	(57.5%)	230
Grand mean	170	230	

Table 4 reveals the frequency distribution of attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the physical health implications of early marriage. One hundred and sixty four (41%) of the respondents has positive attitude that early marriage can expose the teenage girl to maternal mortality while 236 (59%) had negative attitude. One hundred and forty three (35.75%) of the respondents had positive attitude that an adolescent mother who marries later can develop complications during pregnancy while 257 (64.25%) has negative attitude on the same issue. To say that a teenage girl

who marries early has chances of suffering eclempsia (fit and convulsion) in pregnancy, 120 (30%) of the respondents had positive attitude while 280 (70%) had negative attitude on the same issue.

One hundred and sixty-five (41.25%) of the respondents had positive attitude that teenage pregnancy which may result from early marriage can lead to premature labour while 235 (58.75%) had negative attitude on the same issue. Two hundred and sixty (65%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can predispose the woman to anaemia in pregnancy while marriage can predispose the woman to anaemia in pregnancy while 140 (35%) had negative attitude on the same issue. Two hundred and forty five (62.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girls to higher risk of sexually transmitted infections while 155 (38.75%) had negative attitude on the same issue. To say that brides of early marriage are at an extremely high risk of contracting WF and RVF, 188 (29.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude while 282 (70.5) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and forty-five (36.25%) of the respondents had positive attitude that young mothers are likely to suffer heavy bleeding in pregnancy while 255(63.75%) had negative attitude on the same issue. From the responses breakdown 1360 (42.5%) of the respondents with a mean of 170 had positive attitude while 1840 (57.5%) with a mean of 230 had negative attitude on the same issue.

Table 5

Responses on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A towards the social health implications of early marriage.

Social health implications of early marriage	Attitudinal positive	Responses Negative	Total
Early marriage denies young girls their right to go to school	296(74%)	104(26%)	400
Women who marry early are more likely to suffer abuse and violence	224(56%)	176(44%)	400
Early marriage can lead to wife abandonment	150(37.5%)	250(62.5%)	400
Early marriage can expose the child bride to inferiority complex	151(37.75%)	249(62.25%)	400
Early marriage can cause wife battering	162(40.5%)	238(59.5%)	400
Early marriage is associated with divorce and separation	120(30%)	280(70%)	400
A mother who marries early may find it difficult in brining up her children.	117(29.25%)	283(70.75%)	400
Work opportunities are limited for youngsters who marry early.	108(27%)	292(73%)	400
Total	1328	1872	3200
Grand percentage	(41.5%)	(58.5%)	
Grand mean	166	234	

Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A towards the social health implications of early marriage. It revealed that 296 (74%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage denies young girls their right to go to school while 104(26%) had negative attitude on the same issue. Two hundred and twenty four (56%) of the respondents had positive attitude that women who marry early are more likely to suffer abuse and violence while 176 (44%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and fifty (fifty (37.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can lead to wife abandonment while two hundred and fifty had negative attitude on the same issue.

To say that early marriage can expose the child bride to inferiority complex 151(37.75%) of the respondents had positive attitude while 249(62.25%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and sixty-two (40.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can cause wife battering while 238(59.5%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and twenty ((30%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage is associated with divorce and separation while 280 (70%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and seventy (29.25%) of the respondents had positive attitude that a mother who marries early may find it difficult in bringing up her children while 283(70.7%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and eight (27%) respondents had positive attitude that work opportunities are limited for youngsters who marry early while 292 (73%) had negative attitude on the same issue. From the responses breakdown 1328 (41.5%) of the respondents with a mean of 166 had positive attitude on the social health implications of early marriage while 1872 (58.5%) with a mean of 234 had negative attitude on the same issue.

Table 6

Responses on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.GA. towards the emotional health implications of early marriage.

Emotional health implications of early marriage	Attitudinal positive	Response Negative	Total
Early marriage expose the adolescent girl to the following:	400		
Stress	140(35%)	260(65%)	
Despair	89(22.25%)	311(77.75%)	400
Depression	128(32%)	272(68%)	400
Feeling of helplessness	133(33.25%)	267(66.75%)	400
Low self-esteem	114(28.5%)	286(71.5%)	400
Sense of personal failure	110(27.5%)	290(72.5%)	400
Suicide/suicidal attempt	100(25%)	300(75%)	400
Frustration	150(37.5%)	250(62.5%)	400
Confusion	108(27%)	292(73%)	400
Fear	140(35%)	260(65%)	400
Total	1212	2788	4,000
Grand percentage	(30.3%)	(69.7%)	
Grand mean	121.2	278.8	

Table 6 reveals the frequency distribution of attitude of secondary school student in Izzi L.G.A toward the emotional health implications of early marriage. One hundred and forty (35%) of the respondents had negative attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to stress while 260(65%) had negative attitude on the same issue. Eighty-nine (22.25%) of the respondent had positive attitude that early marriage can expose a teenager to despair while 311 (77.75%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and twenty-eight 128(32%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to depression, while 272 (68%) had negative attitude on the same issue.

One hundred and thirty three (33.25%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to feeling of helplessness while 267(68%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and fourteen (28.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose an adolescent girl to low self-esteem/while 286 (71.5%) had negative attitude on the same issue. To say that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to sense of personal failure 110(27.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude while 290 (72.5%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred (25%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to suicide/suicidal attempt while 300(75%) had negative attitude on the same issue.

One hundred fifty respondents (37.5%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to frustration while 250 (62.5%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and eight (27%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose a teenage girl to confusion while 292(73%) had negative attitude on the same issue. One hundred and forty (35%) of the respondents had positive attitude that early marriage can expose the adolescent girl to fear while 260 (65%) had negative attitude on the same issue. From the responses breakdown 1212(30.3%) of the respondents with a mean of 121.2 had positive attitude on emotional health implications of early marriage while 2788 (69.7%) with mean of 278.8 had negative attitude on the same issue.

Table 7

Chi-square analysis testing the hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female student in their attitude towards the health implications of early marriage.

S/N	Gender	Attitudinal positive	Response Negative	Total
	Gender	50(35.71%)	90(64.29%)	140(35%)
	Males	66(25.38%)	194(74.62%)	260(65%)
	Females			
	Total	116(29%)	284(71%)	400

Calculated X^2 value = 4.72

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tabulated } X^2 \text{ value} &= 3.84 \\ \text{Df} &= (r-1) \\ &= (2-1) \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

P<.05

Since X^2 cal. Value of 4.72 is greater than x^2 tab. Value of 3.84 with $df = 1$, and at .05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected and conclusion drawn that there is a significant influence of gender on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi, L.G.A. toward the health implications of early marriage.

Table 8

Chi -square analysis testing the hypothesis of no significant difference among students of various ages in their attitude towards the health implications of early marriage.

Age	Attitudinal positive	Response Negative	Total
13-14 years	18(40%)	27(60%)	45(11.25%)
15-16 years	53(35.33%)	97(64.6%)	150(37.5%)
17-18 years	96(76.8%)	29(23.2%)	125(31.25%)
19 years and above	60(75%)	20(25%)	80(20%)
Total	227(56.75%)	173(43.25%)	400

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Calculated } X^2 \text{ value} &= 64.51 \\ \text{Tabulated } x^2 \text{ value} &= 7.82 \\ \text{Df} &= 3 \\ \text{P} &< .05 \end{aligned}$$

Since x^2 cal. Value of 64.51 is greater than x^2 tab. Value of 7.82 with $df = 3$, and at .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and conclusion drawn that there is a significant influence of age on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the health implications of early marriage.

Table 9

Chi-square analysis testing the hypothesis of no significant difference between boarders and day students in their attitude toward the health implications of early marriage.

S/N		Attitudinal Positive	Response Native	Total
	Types of studentship			
	Boarding students	35(31.82%)	75(68.18%)	110(27.5%)
	Day Students	190(65.52%)	100(34.48%)	290(72.5%)
	Total	227(56.75%)	175(43.75%)	400

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Calculated } x^2 \text{ value} &= 36.85 \\ \text{Tabulated } x^2 \text{ value} &= 3.84 \\ \text{Df} &= (r-1)(c-1) \\ &= (2-1)(2-1) \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

P<.05

Since x^2 cal. Value of 36.85 is greater than x^2 tab. Value of 3.84 with $df = 1$, and at .05 level of significance the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and concluded that there is a significant influence of types studentship on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. toward the health implications of early marriage.

Objective on sought to ascertain the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the physical health implications of early marriage. Result (Table 4) revealed that the attitude of secondary school students towards the physical health implications of early marriage is negative as (57.5%) showed negative responses while 42.5% exhibited positive responses. This is not surprising as this is one of the happening things in our societies. Parents especially mothers always hope that their daughters get married early enough so as to help reduce family expenses. This is in

agreement with the observation of [18], Poverty is one of the major factors underpinning early marriage. This children because of their economic situations try to buy the ideas of their parent that early is good for them.

Objectives two sought to ascertain the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A towards the social health implications of early marriage, the result (Table 5) revealed that the students showed negative attitudes (58,5%) towards the social health implications of early marriage. This not surprising as this child keep hearing the mothers tell their young girls I got married to your father before your age. The children will begin to feel that if their mothers got married before their age and they are still leaving happily with their husbands, that they themselves can still make it if they marry early. They may also have the belief that marrying early will help to save them from some problems of life such as getting involved in teenage pregnancy. This is in line with the view of [25] who stated that it helps to prevent premarital sex. Some religious organizations encourage early marriage as a way to prevent their daughters becoming pregnancy out of wedlock.

Objectives three sought to determine the attitude of secondary school students in izzi L.G.A. towards the emotional health implications of early marriage. Result of the study (Table 6) revealed that majority (69.7%) of the students showed negative attitude while few (30.3%) showed positive attitude towards the emotional health implication of early marriage. This is expected because these children in most cases think in line with their parents. Environments also have effect on the way a person think or act. These children because of lack of exposure are most seemed to behave and think as their parents who see early marriage as the ultimate[21].

Objective four sought to ascertain the influence of gender on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A towards the health implications of early marriage. Result of the study (Table 7) revealed that there is a significant influence of gender on the attitude of secondary school students towards the health implications of early marriage. Women suffer more of early marriage than men. It was observed that girl child marriage is becoming rampant today. Angel (2000) supported that assertion by saying that child brides may suffer vulnerability to HIV/AIDS. Being young and female in African is a major risk factor for infection and young girls are being infected at a considerably disproportional rate to that of boys [26].

Objectives five sought to determine the influence of age on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the health implications of early marriage. Result of the study (Table 8) revealed that there is a significant influence of age on the attitude of secondary school students towards the health implications of early marriage. This is not surprising because it is expected. The older adolescent girls who may have passed through the secondary sexual development may begin to see themselves as big girls Who Should be planning to marry while the young ones will have a different opinion about life at that stage of life. The older students when they marry may not face half of the risks the younger ones will face when they marry. This is agreement with the view of [7] which reported that girls age 10-14 years are five times more likely to die in pregnancy or childbirth than women aged 20-24 years and girls aged 15-19 are twice as likely to die.

Objective six sought to ascertain the influence of types of studentship on the attitude of secondary school students in Izzi L.G.A. towards the health implications of early marriage. The result of the study (Table 9) revealed that there is a significant influence of types of studentship on the attitude of secondary school students toward the health implications of early marriage. This is not surprising because the two types of studentship view things in different ways. Those students who are living in the boarding house who may have come in contact with students from different background may be planning to study further after their secondary education while the day students may be planning to join the world immediately after their secondary school to start making money and this they feel can only be achieved by getting married [28].

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

An appreciable (57.5%) of the students in Izzi L.G.A. had negative attitude while few (42.5%) had positive attitude towards the physical health implications of early marriage.

An appreciation (58.5%) of the students had negative attitude while few (41.5%) had positive attitude towards the social health implications of early marriage.

Majority (69.7%) of the students had negative attitude while few (30.3%) had positive attitude towards the emotional health implications of early marriage.

Gender had a significant influence on the attitude of secondary school students towards the health implications of early marriage

Age had a significant influence on the attitude of secondary school students towards the health implications of early marriage

Types of studentship had a significant influence on the attitude of secondary school students towards the health implication of early marriage (Table 9).

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